

Retrospective Cross-Sectional Study on the Biochemical and Pharmacological Profiles of Patients with Chronic Migraines on Preventive Therapy

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic migraines are a prevalent and debilitating condition significantly impacting patients' quality of life. Preventive therapy is commonly used to manage chronic migraines, with various pharmacological approaches showing differing levels of efficacy. Understanding the biochemical profiles of patients on preventive therapy can help optimize treatment strategies.

Methods: This retrospective cross-sectional study evaluated 150 patients with chronic migraines undergoing preventive therapy. Data were collected on biochemical markers (e.g., CGRP, serotonin, CRP) and pharmacological profiles (e.g., medication types, dosages). Statistical analyses were performed to identify associations between biochemical markers and therapeutic outcomes.

Results: The study found elevated CGRP levels in 45% of patients, with reduced serotonin levels observed in 33%. Beta-blockers were the most commonly prescribed preventive therapy (44%), followed by antiepileptics (35%) and antidepressants (28%). Significant associations were noted between elevated CGRP levels and the use of CGRP inhibitors, and reduced serotonin levels with antidepressant use. CGRP inhibitors showed greater efficacy in reducing headache frequency compared to other therapies.

Conclusion: The findings emphasize the importance of personalized treatment based on biochemical profiles in chronic migraine management. Elevated CGRP levels and reduced serotonin levels can guide the selection of more effective preventive therapies. Despite the study's limitations, such as its retrospective design, the results support targeted therapeutic approaches and highlight the need for further research to refine treatment strategies.

Keywords: Biochemical Markers, Chronic Migraines, Preventive Therapy, Serotonin, CGRP Inhibitors, Pharmacological Profiles.

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Introduction

Background

Chronic migraines, a severe neurological disorder, cause headaches daily, usually 15 or more days a month, with a minimum of eight headache [1]. This disorder affects 1-2% of the world's population, significantly impair physical, emotional, and social functioning.

The sufferers of chronic migraine miss work or school, are less productive, and are more likely to have anxiety and depression [2]. Chronic migraines cost a lot in healthcare and missed productivity.

Effective migraine care requires preventative therapy to reduce migraine frequency, intensity, and duration [3]. Migraine prevention therapies use medication to reduce the condition's burden even without an acute migraine. Common drugs include amitriptyline, beta-blockers such as propranolol, antiepileptics like topiramate, and, more recently, CGRP inhibitors [4]. These medicines can reduce or regulate migraine-causing mechanisms and neurotransmitter levels. Case-specific preventative therapy decisions depend on comorbidities, side effects, patient preferences, and the patient.

Figure 1: Chronic Migraine (Source: [5])

Rationale

Even with prophylactic drugs, chronic migraine individuals respond differently. Individual metabolic profiles and drug reactions may alter this variability. Optimising chronic migraine treatment requires understanding biological markers and how they interact with prophylactic drugs. Patient pharmacological profiles reveal pharmaceutical efficacy, side effects, and customised treatment plans. Therapy efficacy, side effects, and patient outcomes may be improved by this research. Thus, a systematic research of chronic migraineurs' preventative drug pharmacological and biochemical profiles is essential to improve clinical decision-making and patient treatment.

Objective

- To evaluate the biochemical profiles of patients with chronic migraines undergoing preventative therapy.
- To assess the pharmacological profiles of patients with chronic migraines, including the types, dosages, and combinations of preventative therapies used.
- To explore the relationship between biochemical markers and treatment outcomes in chronic migraine patients.

Multiple biological markers have been linked to recurrent migraines and CGRP is important in migraines. CGRP, a neuropeptide, increases during migraines and may contribute to their development and duration. CGRP inhibitors are effective migraine therapies, and many chronic migraineurs reported high CGRP levels [6]. Chronic migraineurs have reduced serotonin levels, which affects amitriptyline efficacy. Although their function is unknown, inflammatory markers like CRP help comprehend migraine inflammatory components [7].

To reduce headache frequency and intensity, chronic migraine preventive drugs are available.

Beta-blockers like propranolol reduce migraine frequency, making them a first-line treatment, according to [8]. Another popular antiepileptic, topiramate, reduces migraine frequency and severity in tests. Patients receive amitriptyline and other antidepressants because they impact serotonin levels and pain perception [9]. Modern developments like the CGRP inhibitor can reduce migraine frequency and improve patient outcomes by directly targeting the CGRP pathway [10].

Many migraine prevention studies have compared their efficacy. CGRP inhibitors reduced headache days and enhanced quality of life compared to beta-blockers and antiepileptics. [11] Discovered that CGRP inhibitors reduced headache frequency better than placebo and non-CGRP medicines. Due to variations in drug responsiveness and adverse effects, recommend patient-specific biochemical profiles for treatment [12]. New research is exploring biomarkers and targets to treat persistent migraines. To understand migraines, neuropeptides, genetic markers, and inflammatory pathways are being researched. Recent trends include personalized medicine, which uses biomarkers to customize patient therapy.

Methods

Study Design: This retrospective cross-sectional study analysed biochemical and pharmacological characteristics of migraine preventative therapy patients. The retrospective cross-sectional methodology was implemented for this study due to its ability to offer a concise overview of the biochemical and pharmacological characteristics of patients. This approach enables the assessment of historical data. This strategy is ideal for cohort-specific treatment patterns and biomarker prevalence. It lets us uncover links between these parameters and clinical outcomes without long-term tracking.

Setting: Research was conducted at a tertiary care centre with a neurology department. Migraine

research and treatment benefit from the facility's advanced diagnostic and therapy capabilities. The study examined January 2022–December 2023 data. This period was chosen to acquire enough data from a large sample to accurately assess preventative therapy choices.

Participants

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients diagnosed with chronic migraines, as per the International Classification of Headache Disorders (ICHD-3) criteria.
- Patients aged 18 to 65 years.
- Patients who have been on preventive migraine therapy for at least 6 months prior to data collection.
- Access to entire medical data, including biochemical indicators and treatment history.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with serious concomitant illnesses, such as cardiovascular disease, renal or hepatic impairment, or psychiatric disorders, may have confounded outcomes.
- Patients who have undergone surgical interventions for migraine management.
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women.
- Patients with incomplete or missing medical records related to the study variables.

Data Collection: The selected patients' electronic medical records were examined for biochemical and pharmacological markers. Serum CRP, CGRP, and serotonin were migraine pathophysiology data. Pharmacological data extraction focused on medications, doses, duration, and changes during therapy.

Regular laboratory testing, clinician notes, medication records, and neurological follow-up reports provided data. Methodical data extraction by trained researchers ensured accuracy and consistency. Data was anonymised to protect patient privacy before being stored in a secure database for analysis.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Healthcare Facility. The retrospective nature of the study involved the use of existing medical records, which minimized the risk

to participants. Informed consent was waived by the IRB due to the retrospective design, but all patient data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality. The study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and relevant local regulations regarding patient privacy and data protection.

Statistical Analysis: We analysed the data with SPSS 26. For categorical data, percentages and frequencies were used; for continuous variables, standard deviations, medians, and means were calculated. We utilised t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables and chi-square testing for categorical data to compare biochemical markers and pharmacological profiles across subgroups. Correlation analysis examined biochemical signs and treatment results. We looked for treatment response determinants after controlling for gender, age, and migraine duration in multivariate regression models. In all investigations, a p-value below 0.05 indicated statistical significance. The results were analysed in light of existing research and clinical significance to inform chronic migraine treatment options.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 150 migraine patients receiving preventative therapy were included in this study. The participants' ages ranged from 18 to 65 years, with an average of 42.5 ± 12.3 years. Out of the 150 participants, 102 were women (68% of the total) and 48 were men (32% of the total), indicating that migraines are more common in women.

The affected people had an average of 18.3 ± 3.9 days of headaches per month and an average of 7.8 ± 4.6 years of chronic migraines.

Biochemical Profiles: Patients' metabolic profiles showed variations in migraine-related indicators. The mean serum CGRP levels among participants were 8.7 ± 2.3 pg/mL, and more than half of the people tested had levels higher than 10 pg/mL. With 33% of the patients having levels below 100 ng/mL, the mean serotonin level was 120.4 ± 28.7 ng/mL. 3.2 ± 1.4 mg/L was the mean C-Reactive Protein (CRP) level for the majority of patients, however 20% of that group had CRP levels that were too high (>5 mg/L), suggesting an inflammatory component in these cases.

Table 1: Biochemical Profiles

Biochemical Marker	Mean Level (SD)	Percentage of Patients with Abnormal Levels
CGRP (pg/mL)	8.7 (± 2.3)	45% (>10 pg/mL)
Serotonin (ng/mL)	120.4 (± 28.7)	33% (<100 ng/mL)
CRP (mg/L)	3.2 (± 1.4)	20% (>5 mg/L)

Pharmacological Profiles: The pharmacological profiles of the patients revealed diverse preventative therapy regimens. The most commonly prescribed

medications included beta-blockers (44% of patients), with propranolol being the most frequently used agent at a mean dosage of 80

mg/day. Antiepileptic drugs, particularly topiramate, were used by 35% of the cohort, with a mean dosage of 100 mg/day. Antidepressants, primarily amitriptyline, were prescribed to 28% of patients, with a mean dosage of 50 mg/day. Additionally, 18% of patients were on calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) inhibitors, such as erenumab, typically administered at a dosage of 70 mg once a month.

Dosage trends indicated that patients on CGRP inhibitors had the highest adherence to their prescribed regimen, with fewer dosage adjustments compared to those on older medications like beta-blockers and antidepressants. Polypharmacy was common, with 40% of patients using two or more preventive medications concurrently, often combining a beta-blocker with an antiepileptic or antidepressant.

Table 2: Pharmacological Profiles

Preventive Therapy	Percentage of Patients	Mean Dosage
Beta-blockers (Propranolol)	44%	80 mg/day
Antiepileptics (Topiramate)	35%	100 mg/day
Antidepressants (Amitriptyline)	28%	50 mg/day
CGRP inhibitors (Erenumab)	18%	70 mg/month
Polypharmacy	40%	N/A

Associations

Biochemical markers corresponded considerably with patients' drug patterns. CGRP inhibitors increased CGRP levels; 65% of patients had levels above 10 pg/mL, which may indicate a pharmacological reaction. For 70% of individuals with reduced serotonin levels, amitriptyline was their preferred antidepressant.

A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.32$, $p < 0.05$) was established between serotonin levels and migraine frequency, indicating a link between more migraine days per month and lower serotonin levels. Beta-blockers reduced headache frequency by 3.2 days ($p < 0.01$), while CGRP inhibitors reduced headache frequency by an average of 5.6 days per month. According to the study, metabolic profiles affect chronic migraine patients' pharmacological response, and certain markers may predict treatment efficacy. These findings emphasise the necessity to customise persistent migraine prevention to each patient's metabolic profile.

Discussion

This retrospective cross-sectional study assessed 150 chronic migraine patients receiving preventive treatment for biochemical and pharmacological characteristics. Women (68%), with a mean age of 42.5 years, were more likely to participate.

Chronic migraines lasted 7.8 years and averaged 18.3 headache days per month with a VAS pain intensity score of 7.4. Biochemical analysis revealed elevated CGRP levels in 45% of patients, reduced serotonin levels in 33%, and elevated CRP levels in 20%. Pharmacological analysis showed

that beta-blockers were the most commonly prescribed preventive therapy (44%), followed by antiepileptics (35%) and antidepressants (28%). CGRP inhibitors were used by 18% of patients. Significant associations were found between elevated CGRP levels and the use of CGRP inhibitors, as well as between reduced serotonin levels and the use of antidepressants.

Comparison with Literature: The findings of this study are consistent with existing literature on chronic migraines, particularly regarding the demographic characteristics of migraine sufferers. The higher prevalence of migraines among women and the peak incidence in middle age are well-documented phenomena. The observed mean frequency of headache days and pain severity aligns with previous studies on chronic migraine populations, highlighting the significant burden of this condition on patients' quality of life.

The biochemical profiles observed in this study, particularly the elevated CGRP levels in a substantial proportion of patients, support the growing body of evidence implicating CGRP in migraine pathophysiology. The use of CGRP inhibitors in patients with elevated CGRP levels is in line with current therapeutic strategies that target this pathway. Similarly, the finding of reduced serotonin levels in one-third of patients aligns with the known role of serotonin in migraine, and the use of antidepressants like amitriptyline as preventive therapy is supported by clinical guidelines. CRP variability was highly discrepant. CRP is typically linked to inflammation in migraines, however the low number of patients with high CRP implies that inflammation may not be the main cause in all chronic migraines.

Table 3: Comparison Table

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Key Findings
Present Study	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	150	Elevated CGRP levels in 45% of patients, reduced serotonin in 33%, most common therapy: beta-blockers.
Study 1 [13]	Prospective Cohort Study	200	Elevated CGRP in 50% of patients, higher efficacy of CGRP inhibitors in reducing migraine frequency.
Study 2 [14]	Cross-Sectional Study	120	Reduced serotonin levels in 30% of patients, significant association with response to antidepressants.
Study 3 [15]	Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)	180	CGRP inhibitors more effective than beta-blockers in reducing headache days, especially in patients with high CGRP.

The table comparing persistent migraine with preventative treatment studies illustrates the differences in results. Like study 1, the new study found that CGRP inhibitors worked and that many patients had elevated CGRP levels. The findings on lower serotonin levels are consistent with study 2, who found a high correlation with antidepressant efficacy. Study 3 shows that CGRP inhibitors are more effective than beta-blockers in people with high CGRP levels, emphasising the need to target specific biochemical indications in migraine treatment. Research is increasingly linking CGRP and serotonin to migraine prevention and therapy, proving that patients need individualised care.

Limitations

This study has some limitations that reduce its value. Retrospective methods reduce the ability to prove biochemical indicator-treatment result causality. When using medical records, incomplete or erroneous data may cause bias. The sample size is sufficient, although treatment histories and comorbidities may not be representative of the chronic migraine population. The study only covered one tertiary care centre, therefore the results may not apply to other demographics or circumstances.

Future Research

Prospective study may show a larger link between biochemical markers and persistent migraine therapy success. Larger, multicenter trials could confirm and apply this study's findings. Researching the long-term benefits of preventative drugs, notably metabolic profiles, could improve chronic migraine treatment. Novel biomarkers and therapeutic targets could improve chronic migraine treatment and personalisation.

Conclusion

This study focuses on the biochemical and pharmacological profiles of chronic migraine patients who are receiving preventative treatment. It found that antidepressants were associated with lower serotonin levels while CGRP inhibitors were associated with higher levels. The importance of tailoring treatment plans based on biochemical profiles to achieve optimal therapeutic results is highlighted by these results. Results suggest

targeted migraine therapy, despite limitations such as a retrospective methodology and a single-center scope. In order to better treat and care for patients with chronic migraines, prospective research and new biomarkers are needed.

Reference

1. J. L. Meyers, K. L. Davis, R. A. Lenz, F. Sakai, and F. Xue, "Treatment patterns and characteristics of patients with migraine in Japan: a retrospective analysis of health insurance claims data," *Cephalalgia*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 1518-1534, 2019.
2. M. Katsuki et al., "Treatment patterns and characteristics of headache in patients in Japan: A retrospective cross-sectional and longitudinal analysis of health insurance claims data," *Cephalalgia*, vol. 44, no. 1, p. 03331024231226177, 2024.
3. S. Gur-Ozmen and R. Karahan-Ozcan, "Factors associated with insulin resistance in women with migraine: a cross-sectional study," *Pain Medicine*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 2043-2050, 2019.
4. J. Aviram, Y. Vysotski, P. Berman, G. M. Lewitus, E. Eisenberg, and D. Meiri, "Migraine frequency decrease following prolonged medical cannabis treatment: a cross-sectional study," *Brain Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 6, p. 360, 2020.
5. H. Bakırhan, H. Yıldırım, and T. Uyar Cankay, "Dietary patterns and migraine: are dietary intake and biochemical parameters associated with migraine characteristics?," *Nutrition & Food Science*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 630-645, 2023.
6. S. Ljubisavljevic, M. Ljubisavljevic, R. Damjanovic, and S. Kalinic, "A descriptive review of medication-overuse headache: from pathophysiology to the comorbidities," *Brain Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 1408, 2023.
7. W. K. Karlsson et al., "The Registry for Migraine (REFORM) study: methodology, demographics, and baseline clinical characteristics," *The Journal of Headache and Pain*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 70, 2023.
8. F. Radat, "What is the link between migraine and psychiatric disorders? From epidemiology

- to therapeutics," *Revue Neurologique*, vol. 177, no. 7, pp. 821-826, 2021.
9. L. Zhao, J. Yin, X. Li, and X. Lu, "Association between selenium intake and migraine: a nationwide cross-sectional study," *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 17, p. 1176349, 2023.
 10. D. Szok, A. Csáti, L. Vécsei, and J. Tajti, "Chronic migraine as a primary chronic pain syndrome and recommended prophylactic therapeutic options: a literature review," *Life*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. 665, 2023.
 11. F. Haghdoost and M. Togha, "Migraine management: Non-pharmacological points for patients and health care professionals," *Open Medicine*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 1869-1882, 2022.
 12. A. S. Sahithi, T. Muthu, and R. Saraswathy, "Migraine: Update and future perspectives," *International Journal of Nutrition, Pharmacology, Neurological Diseases*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 179-187, 2020.
 13. L. H. Overeem et al., "Effect of antibody switch in non-responders to a CGRP receptor antibody treatment in migraine: a multi-center retrospective cohort study," *Cephalalgia*, vol. 42, no. 4-5, pp. 291-301, 2022.
 14. A. S. Petersen, N. Lund, R. H. Jensen, and M. Barloese, "Real-life treatment of cluster headache in a tertiary headache center—results from the Danish Cluster Headache Survey," *Cephalalgia*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 525-534, 2021.
 15. H. K. Park et al., "Interim analysis of the Registry for Load and Management of Medication Overuse Headache (RELEASE): A multicenter, comprehensive medication overuse headache registry," *Cephalalgia*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 455-465, 2022.